

NOVO TESTE

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11     "https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/feature
12     "https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/"
13   "potentialAction": {
14     "@type": "SearchAction",
15     "target": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/pages/search_result",
16     "query-input": "required name=search_term"
17   }},
18   {
19     "@context": "https://schema.org/",
20     "@type": "VideoObject",
21     "name": "5 elementos chave na construção de um site",
22     "@id": "https://youtu.be/mLpWVAoKB3A",
23     "datePublished": "2020-01-17",
24     "description": "5 elementos chave na construção de um site",
25     "thumbnailURL": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png",
26     "thumbnail": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png",
27     "duration": "T1M47S",
28     "uploadDate": "2020-01-17",
29     "author": {
30       "@type": "Corporation",
31       "name": "Marketing Digital Tools"
32     }
33   },
34 {
35   "@context": "http://schema.org",
36   "@type": "webPage",
37   "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos",
38   "mainEntityOfPage": {
39     "@type": "WebPage",
40     "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos/",
41     "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
42     "description": "Planos e Preços"
43   } },
44 {
45   "@context": "http://schema.org",
46   "@type": "BlogPosting",
47   "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Blog",
48   "image": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-VISIBILIDADE.png",
49   "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/como-criar-um-site-e-commerce/",
50   "headline": "Como criar um site e-commerce?",
51   "alternativeHeadline": "Marketing Digital Tools explica",
52   "dateCreated": "2020-01-23",
53   "datePublished": "2020-01-23",
54   "dateModified": "2020-01-23",
55   "inLanguage": "pt-PT",
56   "isFamilyFriendly": "true",
57   "copyrightYear": "2020",
58   "copyrightHolder": "Marketing Digital Tools",
59   "contentLocation": {
60     "@type": "Place",
61     "name": "Porto, PT"
62   },
63   "accountablePerson": {
64     "@type": "Person",
65     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
66     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
67   },
68   "author": {
69     "@type": "Person",
70     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
71     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
72   },
73   "creator": {
74     "@type": "Person",
75     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
76     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
77   },
78   "publisher": {
79     "@type": "Organization",
80     "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com",
81     "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
82     "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com",
83     "logo": {
84       "@type": "ImageObject",
85       "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png"
86     }
87   }
88 }

```

Detetado: ProfessionalService 0 ERROS 2 AVISOS 7 ITENS

ProfessionalService	0	0	0 ERROS	2 AVISOS	1 ITEM
ID: http://marketingdigitaltools.com/ProfessionalService					
BlogPosting / Organization	0	0	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@id					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/ProfessionalService
VideoObject	0	0	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
description					Agência de Marketing Digital
Service / WebPage	0	0	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
url					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png
WebSite	0	0	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
image					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Marketing-Digital-Tools-HP-Image-1.png
FAQPage	0	0	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
image					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-VISIBILIDADE.png
image					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-NOTORIEDADE.png
image					http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-ECOMMERCE.png
sameAs					https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/
sameAs					https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools
sameAs					https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/
sameAs					https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools
sameAs					https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/feature
foundingDate					2020
priceRange					€250 - €749
hasMap					https://www.google.com/maps/place/Marketing+Digital+Tools/@41.1738125,-8.5822565,17z/data=!4m13!1m7!3m6!1s0x0:0x0!2s8CHH5CF9%2BGX!3b1!8m2!3d41.1738125!4d-8.5800625!3m4!1s0xd2465e09d845931:0x4bc565baec63c53a!8m2!3d41.1738461!4d-8.5800649
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address					
@type					PostalAddress
streetAddress					Rua de Santo António de Contumil, 651